

Electronic spectra and excited state properties of triptycene in solution

Fuat Bayrakçeken and Ali Yaman*

Yeditepe University, Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering, Uskudar 81160, Istanbul, Turkey

E-mail : ayaman@science.ankara.edu.tr Fax : 90-312-2232395

Manuscript received 19 September 2000, accepted 10 January 2001

Absorption, emission and some excited state lifetimes are measured at room temperature and at 77 K in solution. *B*-Type delayed fluorescence decay time is reported for the first time for triptycene. The results are compared with the findings of photolysis, flash photolysis and laser flash photolysis experiments.

Triptycene has been given much attention since its first synthesis by Bartlett and Lewis¹, owing to its rigid cage structure. A considerable number of studies have been carried out about electronic spectra of triptycene and its derivatives.

On the basis of appreciable spectral difference between triptycene and triphenylmethane in absorption maxima as well as in extinction coefficient, Bartlett and Lewis¹ ascribed the difference to the presence of intramolecular charge transfer (cross-ring interaction) in triptycene. On the other hand, Wilcox and Craig² calculated the UV-spectrum of triptycene and a few ring-substituted triptycene and concluded that the spectra of these compounds could be regarded as the superposition of three benzenoid chromophores.

Photochemical isomerization of triptycene was studied by Walsh³, and Turro *et al.*⁴. They found that triptycene produces a single yellow isomer ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 249$ and 345 nm, $\log \epsilon = 4.26$ and 3.89, respectively) upon direct irradiation (photolysis) in dilute ether or acetone solution. This product was neither the anticipated semibullvalene nor a cyclooctatetraene derivative. The conversion of triptycene to photo-product was thought to be a very fast triplet rearrangement. Since formation of photo-product was also observed in photolysis at 77 K, unless the rate of this rearrangement processed a remarkably large temperature coefficient, it appeared unlikely that the reaction occurs from T_1 ^{2,5}. Hashimoto *et al.*⁶ reported the synthesis, optical resolution and absolute configuration of triptycene. Some excited state reactions, crystal structure and photo-rearrangement of triptycene were also studied^{7,8}.

Results and Discussion

In photolysis experiments there is no possibility to observe the formation of triplet state of triptycene. Since phosphorescence and *B*-type delayed fluorescence of triptycene⁷ are observable, we may write the following :

(creation of excited singlet and lowest triplet state)

(*E*-type delayed fluorescence)

(*B*-type delayed fluorescence via excited triplet⁷)

(*R*-type delayed fluorescence via singlet state)

(*R*-type delayed fluorescence via triplet state)

Here, 1M = ground state, ${}^1M^*$ = singlet excited state, ${}^3M^*$ = lowest triplet state, ${}^3M^{**}$ = lowest excited triplet state, ${}^1M^+$ = positive ion of triptycene, e^- = free electron.

Photochemical studies of triptycene by conventional flash photolysis reveal that the excited triptycene formed in the primary step subsequently undergoes a variety of processes, triplet formation, isomerization, ion production etc. Irradiation of triptycene results in the smooth formation of one photo-product which is very stable molecule. For fluorescence and phosphorescence studies one or two photon absorption spectra cannot give valuable informa-

*Permanent address : Ankara University, Department of Physics, Tandogan, 06100 Ankara, Turkey.

Fig. 1. Excitation spectrum of triptycene in cyclohexane at room temperature ($\lambda_{ex} = 280$ nm).

tion. For this reason we preferred to use the information of the excitation spectrum of triptycene. Fig. 1 shows the excitation spectrum of triptycene in cyclohexane at room

Fig. 2. Phosphorescence spectrum of triptycene in cyclohexane at 77 K ($\lambda_{ex} = 280$ nm).

Fig. 3. Triplet-triplet absorption spectrum of triptycene in cyclohexane at room temperature.

temperature. Fig. 2 shows phosphorescence spectrum of triptycene at 77 K and Fig. 3 *T-T* absorption spectrum of triptycene in cyclohexane at room temperature. Fig. 4 shows the lowest triplet state decay of triptycene in cyclohexane at room temperature in the presence of air dif-

Fig. 4. Lowest triplet state decay of triptycene in cyclohexane at room temperature; wavelength = 425 nm.

fusion into the solution and the measured lifetime of the lowest triplet is found to be 704 ns. This lifetime is not long enough to create *E* and/or *P* type delayed fluorescence. Fig. 5 shows *B*-type delayed fluorescence decay at

Fig. 5. *B*-Type delayed fluorescence decay of triptycene in cyclohexane at room temperature; wavelength = 380 nm.

380 nm and the lifetime is found to be 307 ns. Triplet-triplet spectrum of triptycene reveals that triptycene triplets are stable at room temperature. This conclusion was reinforced by the appearance of all kinds of delayed fluorescences. Due to the noisy signals and short lifetime of the lowest triplet state, decay times of *E* and *P* type delayed fluorescences are not reported here. But estimated decay times were in agreement with the triplet lifetime. The identity of the delayed fluorescence and prompt fluorescence spectra excludes the possibility of the triplet state spectra observed being due to an impurity with a low-lying triplet state or an isomer or a photo-product. The formation of one

photo-product, phosphorescence emissions, radiationless transitions from triplet state to ground state and triplet-triplet annihilation decreased the triplet state of triptycene concentration. Therefore, triplet-triplet absorption spectra is weakly observed (i.e. absorbance values are lower than usual) at room temperature. The concentrations of the samples were between 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} M for all the experiments. Best concentration used were 2.5×10^{-4} M. As it is seen from Fig. 2, there are two small Raman blips on the top of the broad phosphorescence spectrum at 362 and 385 nm. Usually all kinds of luminescence swamps the Raman signal. At 77 K, the vicinity of the samples are cloudy, therefore scattering occurs.

Experimental

Triptycene was purified by repeated crystallization in high vacuum line (background pressure 10^{-7} torr). All other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Absorption spectra were recorded using a Cary-219 spectrophotometer. Singlet and triplet related transient phenomena were studied in a laser flash photolysis set-up consisting of the following : a Molelectron UV-400 nitrogen laser system at 337.1 nm, Nd : YAG laser at 1064, 532 and 266 nm, excimer laser at 248 nm and a dye laser at 300–650 nm band for excitation. A kinetic absorption spectrophotometer with nanosecond response (pulsed 500-W, xenon lamp B&L, UV-visible high intensity monochromator, and RCA-4840 photomultiplier tube with output signal terminated into 93 ohm). A tektronix 7912 digitizer and LSI-11 microprocessor unit controlled the experiments and processed the data at the initial state. The data from LSI-11 were finally transferred to a time-shared PDP11/55 computer system for storage and further treatment. Selected concentrations were between 10^{-4} and 10^{-5} M.

Acknowledgement

This research was carried out partly at Department of Electrical and Electronics of Yeditepe University and at Department of Engineering Physics of Ankara University.

References

1. P. D. Bartlett and E. S. Lewis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 1005.
2. C. F. Wilcox and A. C. Craig, 1961, **26**, 2491.
3. T. D. Walsh, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 515.
4. N. J. Turro, M. Tobin, L. Friedman and J. B. Hamilton, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 516.
5. C. F. Wilcox, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, **33**, 1874.
6. M. Hashimoto, Y. Shimizu, F. Ogura and M. Nakagawa, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, **47**, 1761.
7. F. Bayrakçeken, *J. Lumin.*, 1992, **54**, 29.
8. H. Iwamura and K. Yoshimura, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 2552; H. Iwamura, *Chem. Lett.*, 1974, 5; T. Hayashi, N. Mataga, Y. Sakata and S. Misumi, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, **48**, 416; P. W. Rabideau, J. W. Paschal and L. E. Patterson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **97**, 5700; R. O. Day, V. W. Day, S. J. Fuernis and D. M. S. Wheeler, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1975, 296; M. Mikami, K. Toriumi, M. Konno and Y. Saito, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1975, **B31**, 2474; M. Oki, M. Matsusue, T. Akinaga, Y. Matsumoto and S. Yoyota, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1994, **67**, 2831; K. Sakakibara and N. L. Allinger, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 4044; A. Ishii, K. Maeda, M. Kodachi, N. Aoyagi, K. Kato, T. Maruta, M. Hoshino and J. Nakayama, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1996, 1277; T. Y. Fu, J. N. Gamlin, G. Olovsson, J. R. Scheffer, J. Trotter and D. T. Young, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1995, **36**, 2025; M. Kubota, K. Hatano, M. Takahashi and Y. Kawada, *J. Elect. Spect. Rel. Phen.*, 1997, **83**, 165; A. Furlan, S. Leutwyler and M. J. Riley, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **109**, 10767; J. C. Bryan, R. A. Sachleben, A. A. Gakh and G. J. Bunick, *J. Chem. Cryst.*, 1999, **29**, 513.